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The Damaskos Mint of Alexander the Great

PLATES 6–14

LLOYD W. H. TAYLOR*

After a brief commissioning period involving the contemporaneous serial striking of coins in each of two series, the newly established Macedonian Imperial mint at Damaskos then produced the bulk of its coinage in a complexly interwoven manner, with a tight interlinking of obverse dies. This was the result of a shared inventory of obverse dies used by up to six striking teams. Inconspicuous patterns of one to six small dots, used as secondary mint controls, may have served to identify the coins struck on each anvil. This would have facilitated the mint's internal control processes, involving the daily accounting for and reconciliation of silver input to each anvil, with the coinage output from each, in a production operation consisting of a large number of striking teams/anvils within a single secure facility. The coinage has the characteristics of a high volume, short duration mintage commencing around 326/5¹ with an estimated duration of about one year. The total coined volume from the mint is estimated to have been 1.22 million tetradrachms, equivalent to c. 807 Attic talents of silver, struck from an estimated 61 obverse dies.

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1. All dates in this article are BC.

INTRODUCTION

The Damaskos mint is one of the least studied and poorly understood of the mints opened by Alexander the Great following his conquest of the eastern Mediterranean. Unlike most of Alexander's mints, Damaskos had no prior history of coinage production. It produced a single denomination of coinage, the tetradrachm, readily distinguished from other mints by the letters ΔΑ, signifying the abbreviated name of the city, placed beneath the *diphros* on the reverse. The absence of any other denominations in the Damaskos emission is notable; unique amongst the larger Macedonian Imperial mints of the time. Yet the coinage of Damaskos was the fourth most voluminous of any city represented in the Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664) leading to the inference that it represented one of the more significant coinages circulating in the east down to 318 BC. In discussing the significance of the content of the Demanhur Hoard, Le Rider noted, "The Damascus mint seems to have been one of the region's most active, so far as silver is concerned, so it is regrettable that no corpus has been undertaken for it."²

Prior Studies

Newell³ identified two series in the mint's output. Series 1 carries a vertically oriented *ΑΧ* mint control on the reverse left field, while Series 2 is characterized by the presence of the forepart of a ram in a similar position. Both series employ a relatively inconspicuous secondary mint control system using a number of dots, or globules in the terminology of Price,⁴ disposed in various positions and patterns beneath the *diphros* on which Zeus is seated.

Newell⁵ identified 17 types in the coinage, based on the various secondary controls that accompanied the primary controls. He counted 51 obverse and 127 reverse dies amongst 244 specimens in the Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664). Newell noted that the various patterns of dots "do not seem to have indicated distinct issues or distinct officinae of the mint." Based on the number and the disposition of dots, or globules, plus one symbol form secondary control, Price defined 19 discrete types in the output of Alexander's Damaskos mint; Price

2. G. Le Rider, *Alexander the Great: Coinage, Finances and Policy*, trans. W. E. Higgins (Philadelphia: American Philosophical Society, 2007), 147.

3. E. T. Newell, "Reattribution of Certain Tetradrachms of Alexander the Great," *AJN* 45/46 (1912): 5–62; E. T. Newell, *Alexander Hoards II Demanhur, 1905*, ANS NM 19 (New York: American Numismatic Society, 1923).

4. M. J. Price, *The Coinage in the Name of Alexander the Great and Philip Arrhidaeus* (London: British Museum/Swiss Numismatic Society, 1991), 398–401.

5. Newell, "Reattribution," 46 and Newell, *Alexander*, 49–50.

types 3197–3215. In Price's sequence of types not only the number of dots, but also their varied arrangements beneath the *diphros* determined the various types.

Newell posited that the Damaskos mint of Alexander III operated in the period 332 to 319, whereas Price suggested a shorter duration of 330 to 320.⁶ Neither Newell, nor Price presented arguments in support of the proposed dates, noting simply the significance of the Demanhur Hoard (*IGCH* 1664) in providing a *terminus ante quem* of 318. Mørkholm suggested that the mint opened shortly after the capture of the city in late 333 “perhaps prompted by the accident that here Alexander acquired the rich booty left by Darius after Issus.”⁷

In view of these uncertainties, the writer undertook a die study of the coinage, the results of which are detailed below.

CATALOGUE

The catalogue is broken into two series. The smaller of the two, Series 1 is characterized by the presence of the $\mathcal{A}X$ mint control in the left field reverse. Series 2 coins bear a ram-forepart in the left field reverse. Each series is divided into a number of sequence types, defined firstly by the absence, or presence of a secondary mint control defined by the number of dots and secondly by their arrangement beneath Zeus's *diphros*, or in one instance, a symbol instead of a dot based control. In this arrangement, the first digit of the catalogue sequence type defines the series (1 or 2) to which it belongs. With one exception, the second digit in the type number defines the number of dots in the secondary mint control; the exception being the sole type bearing an ivy leaf symbol. The third digit in the sequence type number is defined by the arrangement and/or placement of the dots beneath the *diphros* of Zeus. For example, type 2.3.1 is the first of the Series 2 type bearing three dots, in this case disposed horizontally above the strut of the *diphros*, in contrast to other arrangements and/or placements of the three dots, of which seven different arrangements are noted i.e. 2.3.1–2.3.7. This sequence and type numbering scheme has the advantage of clearly identifying the relevant series to which a coin belongs (first digit), the type of secondary control in terms of the number of dots (second digit), or a symbol (in the case of 2.7.1), and the various arrangements and/or placement of dots (third digit). This sequence type numbering can be expanded easily to accommodate new configurations of the dot controls, should they be identified in future studies.

6. Newell, *Alexander*, 48–50; Price, *Coinage*, 398–401.

7. O. Mørkholm, *Early Hellenistic coinage from the Accession of Alexander to the Peace of Apamea (336–186 B.C.)*, ed. P. Grierson and U. Westermark (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1991), 46.

In the catalogue, illustrated coins are denoted by an asterisk in the first column. Obverse dies (column two) are numbered sequentially, while reverse dies (column three) are numbered sequentially within each group. Coin weights (column four) are in grams. All coins were struck with dies adjusted towards 12h (variance 10h–2h). All coins bear a standard iconography and epigraphy:

Obv.: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.

Rev.: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ on r., Zeus seated l. on *diphros*, holding eagle and sceptre, dotted border.

Series 1

1.0.1 ΑΧ, ΔΑ. (Price 3197)

1.*	A1	P1	17.17	ANS 1947.98.269.	P1 right hand of Zeus portrayed with facing open palm, fingers splayed.
2.*	A1	P2	17.18	London, BM 1911,0704.39.	Henceforth the right hand of Zeus portrayed in profile with upward orientation.
3.	A2	P3	17.04	Aureo and Calico 295–1 (5 Jul. 2017), Lot 10; G&M 225 (14 Oct. 2014), Lot 1339.	
4.	A2	P3	17.21	Lanz 149 (24 Jun. 2010), Lot 122.	
5.*	A2	P3	17.14	ANS 1944.100.34302.	
6.	A2	P4	17.21	London, BM 2002,0101.720.	
7.	A2	P4	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34303.	
8.	A2	P5	17.20	G&M 156 (5 Mar. 2007), Lot 1275.	
9.	A2	P5	17.22	CNG, inventory no. 787315.	
10.	A2	P5	17.02	ANS 1944.100.34304.	
11.	A2	P6	17.14	ANS 1944.100.34305.	

- | | | | | | |
|---|----|----|-------|--|--|
| 12. | A2 | P6 | 17.21 | G&M 156 (5 Mar. 2007), Lot 1274. | |
| 13. | A2 | P6 | 17.11 | Heritage (6 Jan. 2013), Lot 21155. | |
| 14. | A2 | P6 | 17.09 | CNG 87 (18 May 2011), Lot 340. | |
| 15. | A2 | P6 | 17.18 | M&M 157 (4 Jun. 2014), Lot 157. | |
| 16. | A2 | P6 | 17.12 | Blackburn Museum, SNG Vol. VIII, 475; SNGuk_0800_0475. | |
| 1.2.1 <i>AX, two dots separated by throne strut, ΔA below. (Price 3199)</i> | | | | | |
| 17.* | A3 | P1 | 17.08 | London Coin Galleries 4 (1–2 Jun. 2017), Lot 394. | A3 early state. Obverse die link to 2.1.1, Cat. No. 100. |
| 18. | A3 | P2 | 17.17 | ANS 1947.98.270. | A3 early state. |
| 19. | A3 | P2 | 17.15 | CNG eAuction 352 (3 Jun. 2015), Lot 66. | A3 early state. |
| 20. | A3 | P2 | 17.11 | London, BM 2002,0101.721. | A3 early state. |
| 1.1.1 <i>AX, dot between throne struts, ΔA below. (Price 3198)</i> | | | | | |
| 21. | A4 | P1 | 17.23 | ANS 1944.100.34313. | A4 early state. |
| 22. | A4 | P1 | 17.15 | London, BM 1908,0110.2354. | |
| 23. | A3 | P1 | 16.40 | ANS 1944.100.34308. | A3 early state. |
| 1.5.1 <i>AX, five dots between throne struts, ΔA below. (Price –)</i> | | | | | |
| 24.* | A3 | P1 | 17.22 | CNG, inventory no. 859317. | A3 with early die breaks in mane and incipient break on forehead. Obverse die link to 2.1.1, Cat. No. 100. |
| 25.* | A4 | P1 | 17.17 | ANS 1944.100.34315. | A4 early state. |

26.	A3	P1	17.03	ANS 1944.100.34312.	A3 moderately worn.
27.	A3	P1	17.02	Noble Numismatics 89 (25–28 Nov. 2008), Lot 3811.	A3 breaks in lion mane.
28.	A4	P1	17.15	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253163.	A4 early die break beneath lion jaw on neck of Herakles.
1.1.1 <i>AX</i> , dot between throne struts, ΔA below. (Price 3198)					
29.*	A3	P2	17.13	ANS 1944.100.34306.	
30.	A3	P2	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34307.	
31.	A3	P3	17.24	CNG 75 (23 May 2007), Lot 137.	A3 early die break on forehead.
1.4.1 <i>AX</i> , four dots between throne struts, ΔA below. (Price 3200)					
32.	A3	P1	17.19	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18202962.	A3 die break on forehead.
33.*	A3	P1	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34310.	
34.	A3	P1	17.13	Lanz 138 (26 Nov. 2007), Lot 296.	
35.	A3	P1	17.09	CNG 37 (20 Mar. 1996), Lot 212.	
36.	A4	P2	17.26	London, BM 1929,0811.70.	Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1664). A4 die breaks on neck.
37.	A4	P2	17.24	Brüder Egger 40 (2 May 1912), Lot 683.	A4 die breaks on neck.
38.	A4	P2	17.15	CNG 35 (20 Sep. 1995), Lot 118.	A4 die breaks on neck.
39.*	A4	P2	16.80	ANS 1944.100.34316.	A4 die breaks on neck.
40.	A3	P3	17.15	ANS 1944.100.34314.	A3 major die breaks and fragmentation in mane. Die here in later state than Cat. No. 100.

- 41.* A3 P4 17.10 ANS 1944.100.34311. A3 major die breaks and fragmentation in mane. Die here in later state than Cat. No. 100.

Series 2

2.0.1 *Ram-forepart r., below throne strut ΔA. (Price 3202)*

- 42.* A5 P1 17.21 ANS 1944.100.34466.
43. A5 P2 16.49 Künker. 158 (28 Sep. 2009), Lot 176.
- 44.* A6 P3 17.15 ANS 1944.100.34468.
45. A6 P3 16.95 Elsen 93 (15 Sep. 2007), Lot 145; Vinchon Sale (13 Apr. 1985), Lot 236.
46. A6 P3 16.61 Pars Coins inventory no. PCW-G5485.
47. A6 P4 17.19 ANS 1944.100.34469.
- 48.* A7 P5 17.20 ANS 1944.100.34481.
49. A7 P5 17.10 London, BM Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1913,0518.3. 1664).
50. A8 P6 17.14 ANS 1944.100.34483.
- 51.* A8 P7 17.12 ANS 1944.100.34484.
52. A8 P8 17.20 ANS 1944.100.34482. P8 fragment broken from die beneath *diphros* seat.
53. A9 P8 17.17 Roma E-Sale 26 (30 Apr. 2016), Lot 127. P8 fragment broken from die beneath *diphros* seat.
- 54.* A9 P9 16.92 Brisbane, LWHT Coll; Eukratides Ancient Numismatics.
55. A9 P10 16.70 CGB.fr Monnaies 11 (30 Nov. 1999), Lot 48.

56.	A9	P10	17.18	Nomos 11 (9 Oct. 2015), Lot 64.	P10 small fragment broken from die in front of Zeus's head. Ram-forepart breaking up.
57.	A9	P11	17.05	ANS 1944.100.34477.	
58.	A9	P12	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34478.	
59.*	A9	P13	17.10	ANS 1944.100.34479.	
60.	A9	P14	16.98	ANS 1944.100.34480.	Abu Hommos Hoard (IGCH 1667).
61.	A9	P15	16.86	London, BM 1908,0110.2352.	
62.	A10	P16	16.86	Agora 49 (2 Feb 2016), Lot 19; Nomos 5 (25 Oct. 2011), Lot 137.	
63.	A10	P16	16.95	ANS 1944.100.34470.	Abu Hommos Hoard (IGCH 1667).
64.*	A10	P17	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34471.	
65.	A10	P18	16.48	ANS 1944.100.34472.	
66.	A10	P19	17.24	ANS 1944.100.34473.	
67.	A10	P20	17.22	CNG, inventory no. 833214.	
68.	A10	P20	16.87	ANS 1974.26.570.	
69.	A10	P21	17.24	ANS 1944.100.34474.	
70.	A10	P22	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34475.	
71.	A10	P23	16.91	ANS 1944.100.34476.	
72.*	A11	P24	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34496.	Type 2 rev.
73.	A11	P25	17.22	London, BM 1910,1104.18.	Type 2 rev.
74.	A11	P25	16.42	ANS 1944.100.34497.	Type 2 rev.
75.	A12	P26	17.18	ANS 1957.172.1263.	Type 2 rev.
76.*	A12	P26	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34499.	Type 2 rev.
77.	A12	P27	16.08	ANS 1944.100.34498.	Abu Hommos Hoard (IGCH 1667). Type 2 rev.

78.*	A13	P28	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34500.	Type 2 rev.
79.	A13	P29	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34501.	Type 2 rev.
80.	A13	P30	17.10	G&M 233 (6 Oct. 2015), Lot 1304.	Type 2 rev.
81.	A13	P31	17.36	CNG 99 (30 May 2015), Lot 70.	Type 2 rev.
82.	A13	P32	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34502.	Type 2 rev.
83.	A13	P32	17.13	Münzhandlung Basel 8 (22 Mar. 1937), Lot 244.	Type 2 rev.
84.*	A14	P33	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34503.	Type 2 rev.
85.	A14	P34	17.26	London, BM 2002,0101.722.	Type 2 rev.
86.	A14	P34	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34504.	Type 2 rev.
87.	A14	P35	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34505.	Type 2 rev.
88.	A14	P35	17.25	CNG, inventory no. 928402.	Type 2 rev.
89.	A14	P36	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34506.	Type 2 rev.
90.	A14	P36	16.88	CNG 39 (18 Sep.1996), Lot 357.	Type 2 rev.
91.	A14	P37	17.04	ANS 1944.100.34507.	Type 2 rev.
92.	A14	P38	17.24	Oxford, HCR23575; SNGuk_0503_2928.	Type 2 rev.
93.	A14	P39	17.20	Lanz 155 (10 Dec. 2012), Lot 106.	Type 2 rev.
94.	A14	P40	17.16	ANS 1947.98.277.	Type 2 rev.
95.	A14	P41	17.08	ANS 1944.100.34508.	Type 2 rev.
96.	A14	P41	17.25	Goldberg 69 (29 May 2012), Lot 3053.	Type 2 rev.
97.	A15	P42	17.18	M&M 31 (23 Oct. 2009), Lot 23.	
98.*	A15	P43	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34467.	A15 die break transects lion scalp.
99.*	A16	P43	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34465.	

2.1.1 *Ram-forepart r., dot above strut, ΔA below. (Price 3203)*

100.*	A3	P1	17.17	Roma eSale 31 (26 Nov. 2016), Lot 62.	A3 obverse die link to 1.5.1, Cat No. 17. A3 with wear and early die breaks.
101.	A10	P2	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34485.	
102.	A10	P3	16.98	ANS 1947.98.271.	
103.	A10	P3	17.19	Triton IV (5 Dec. 2000), Lot 166.	
104.	A11	P4	17.19	Oxford, HCR23577; SNGuk_0503_2930.	Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664).
105.	A11	P4	15.52	ANS 1944.100.34495.	
106.	A12	P5	17.11	ANS 1947.98.276.	Type 2 rev.
107.	A13	P6	17.19	London, BM 1964,1203.58.	Type 2 rev.
108.	A13	P6	17.03	Adolph E. Cahn 80 (27 Feb. 1933), Lot 168.	Type 2 rev.
109.	A13	P7	15.50	Ancient Numismatic Enterprise inventory no. 4294.	Type 2 rev.
110.	A14	P8	17.22	London, BM 1929,0811.71.	Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664).Type 2 rev.
111.	A14	P8	17.17	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253126.	Type 2 rev.
112.	A15	P9	17.21	Oxford, HCR23576; SNGuk_0503_2929.	Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664).
113.	A15	P10	16.90	NumisCorner Vcoins store inventory no. 61598.	
114.	A15	P10	17.26	ANS 1944.100.34358.	
115.	A15	P11	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34359.	

2.0.2 *No mint controls. (Price 3201)*

116.*	A17	P1	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34464.	A17 in earliest state.
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- 2.1.1 *Ram-forepart r., dot above strut, ΔA below. (Price 3203)*
- | | | | | | |
|-------|-----|-----|-------|---|---|
| 117. | A17 | P12 | 17.19 | CNG 45 (18 Mar. 1998) Lot 202. | A17 with light wear. |
| 118. | A17 | P12 | 17.22 | ANS 1944.100.34324. | |
| 119. | A17 | P12 | 17.23 | Lanz 97 (22 May 2000), Lot 191. | |
| 120. | A17 | P13 | 16.31 | ANS 1944.100.34325. | |
| 121. | A17 | P14 | 17.07 | G&M 220 (11 Mar. 2014), Lot 1191. | |
| 122. | A17 | P14 | 17.18 | Numismatik Naumann 49 (8 Jan. 2017), Lot 129. | |
| 123. | A17 | P15 | 17.16 | CNG, inventory no. 788359. | |
| 124.* | A18 | P15 | 17.17 | ANS 1944.100.34351. | |
| 125. | A18 | P16 | 17.17 | ANS 1944.100.34352. | |
| 126. | A18 | P16 | 17.15 | ANS 1944.100.34353. | |
| 127.* | A19 | P17 | 17.20 | ANS 1944.100.34361. | Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1664). |
| 128. | A19 | P17 | 17.00 | ANS 1944.100.34317. | Abu Hommos Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1667). |
| 129. | A20 | P18 | 17.19 | London, BM 1913,0518.13. | Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1664). A20 breaking up beneath neck. |
| 130. | A20 | P18 | 17.07 | CNG eAuction 72 (3 Sep. 2003), Lot 8. | A20 breaking up beneath neck. |
| 131.* | A20 | P18 | 17.11 | ANS 1944.100.34318. | A20 breaking up beneath neck. |
| 132. | A20 | P18 | 16.87 | Chaponnière & Firmenich SA 6 (22 Nov 2016), Lot 1523. | A20 breaking up beneath neck. |
| 133. | A20 | P19 | 17.13 | ANS 1944.100.34319. | A20 with major die break beneath neck. |

134.	A20	P20	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34320.	A20 with major die break beneath neck.
135.	A20	P21	17.20	Meister & Sonntag 16 (27 Nov. 2012), Lot 1008.	A20 with major die break beneath neck.
136.	A20	P21	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34321.	A20 with major die break beneath neck.
137.	A21	P22	17.11	ANS 1944.100.34322.	
138.*	A21	P23	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34323.	
139.	A22	P24	17.24	ANS 1944.100.34326.	
140.*	A22	P25	17.10	ANS 1944.100.34327.	
141.	A23	P26	17.09	ANS 1944.100.34328.	
142.*	A23	P27	17.12	ANS 1944.100.34329.	
143.	A23	P28	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34334.	
144.	A23	P29	16.68	ANS 1944.100.34335.	
145.*	A24	P30	17.13	ANS 1944.100.34332.	
146.	A24	P31	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34333.	
147.	A24	P32	17.10	ANS 1944.100.34330.	
148.	A24	P33	17.11	ANS 1944.100.34331.	
149.*	A25	P33	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34336.	
150.*	A26	P34	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34338.	
151.	A26	P35	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34337.	
152.	A27	P36	17.01	CNG, inventory no. 884869.	
153.	A27	P36	17.2	ANS 1944.100.34340.	
154.*	A27	P37	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34339.	
155.	A27	P38	17.22	CNG eAuction 341 (17 Dec. 2014), Lot 1.	
156.	A28	P39	17.25	ANS 1944.100.34341.	
157.	A28	P39	17.40	Brüder Egger 60 (2 July 1928), Lot 435.	
158.	A28	P40	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34342.	

159.	A28	P40	17.15	Copenhagen (SNG Cop. 792).	
160.*	A29	P41	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34343.	
161.*	A30	P41	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34344.	
162.	A31	P41	17.11	CNG eAuction 294 (16 Jan. 2011), Lot 268.	
163.*	A31	P42	17.00	ANS 1944.100.34345.	
164.	A32	P43	17.05	London, BM 1881,0102.39.	Kuft Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1670). A32 worn. P43 dot above topmost strut.
165.*	A32	P44	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34349.	A32 worn.
166.*	A33	P45	17.11	Stack's (10 Sep. 2008), Lot 51.	
167.*	A34	P46	17.21	Oxford, HCR9625; SNGuk_0503_2931; Sotheby (19 Mar. 1951) Lot 75.	Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1664).
168.	A34	P47	17.25	ANS 1944.100.34350.	Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1664).
169.*	A35	P47	17.24	Gemini VII (9 Jan. 2011), Lot 274.	
170.	A35	P48	17.18	Heritage 3031 (20 Jan. 2014), Lot 27022.	
171.	A35	P49	17.09	Naville I (4 Apr. 1921), Lot 916; ex-Pozzi Coll.	
172.*	A36	P50	17.15	London, BM 1913,0518.5.	Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1664).
173.	A36	P50	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34354.	
174.*	A37	P51	16.94	ANS 1944.100.34355.	
175.*	A38	P52	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34356.	
176.*	A39	P53	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34357.	
177.*	A40	P54	17.00	Ancient Delights VCoins Store.	

178.	A40	P54	17.03	Nomos Obolos 5 (26 Jun 2016), Lot 128.	
179.	A40	P54	17.04	H. D. Rauch GmbH 74 (7 Dec. 2004), Lot 145.	
180.*	A41	P55	17.11	ANS 1944.100.34360.	
181.	A41	P56	17.17	Ars Coin Wien 1 (4 Jan. 2015), Lot 42.	
182.*	A42	P57	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34486.	
183.*	A43	P58	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34491.	
184.	A43	P59	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34488.	
185.	A43	P60	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34490.	
186.	A43	P61	16.89	Paris, BNF41838016.	Coin holed.
187.	A43	P62	17.11	CNG eAuction 92 (23 Jun. 2004), Lot 13.	
188.*	A44	P63	17.26	ANS 1944.100.34493.	
189.	A44	P64	16.84	ANS 1944.100.34494.	P64 crescent-shaped fragment broken from die before eagle's head.
190.*	A45	P65	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34496.	
2.1.2 <i>Ram-forepart r, beneath throne strut a dot above ΔA. (Price -)</i>					
191.	A42	P1	16.94	London, BM 1949,0411.280.	Possibly an example of 2.2.6 with the second dot beneath ΔA struck off flan.
2.2.2 <i>Ram-forepart r, two dots vertically above strut, ΔA below. (Price 3204)</i>					
192.	A11	P1	17.20	Zuzim VCoins store, inventory no. g624.	Type 2 rev.
193.	A11	P2	17.18	London, BM 1912,0905.30.	Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664). Type 2 rev.
194.	A11	P2	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34515.	Type 2 rev.
195.	A12	P3	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34516.	Type 2 rev.

196.	A12	P4	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34517.	Type 2 rev.
197.	A12	P5	17.00	G&M 236 (7 Mar. 2016), Lot 152A.	Type 2 rev.
198.	A12	P5	17.14	HJB, inventory no. cc72129.	Type 2 rev.
199.	A13	P5	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34518.	Type 2 rev.
200.	A14	P6	17.22	Oxford, HCR23579; SNGuk_0503_2932.	Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664). Type 2 rev.
201.	A14	P6	17.22	ANS 1980.109.39.	Type 2 rev.
202.*	A14	P7	17.01	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; CNG, inventory no. 412444.	Type 2 rev.
203.	A14	P7	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34512.	Type 2 rev.
204.	A14	P7	17.00	ANS 1944.100.34519.	Type 2 rev.
205.	A14	P7	17.04	Madison, Wis., Chazen Museum of Art; <i>Ancient Coins at the Elvehjem Museum of Art</i> , 61.	Type 2 rev.
206.	A14	P8	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34520.	Type 2 rev.
207.	A14	P9	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34521.	Type 2 rev.
208.	A14	P10	17.23	HJB, inventory no. cc72128.	Type 2 rev.
209.	A14	P10	17.02	London, BM 1908,0110.2353.	Type 2 rev.
210.	A18	P11	17.07	CNG 88 (28 Apr. 2004), Lot 39.	
211.	A18	P11	17.08	Heritage. 3032 (10 Apr. 2014), Lot 23110.	
212.	A25	P12	16.91	CNG eAuction 311 (25 Sep. 2013), Lot 551.	
213.	A25	P13	17.15	ANS 1944.100.34366.	
214.	A25	P14	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34392.	

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| 215. | A22 | P15 | 17.12 | ANS 1944.100.34362. | P15 vertical die break above dots. |
| 216. | A23 | P15 | 17.17 | ANS 1944.100.34364. | P15 vertical die break extends through dots. |
| 217. | A25 | P15 | 17.00 | CNG eAuction 128 (7 Dec. 2005), Lot 25. | A25 in most worn state with many die breaks. P15 die break most advanced. |
| 218. | A24 | P16 | 17.22 | ANS 1944.100.34365. | |
| 219. | A24 | P16 | 17.00 | M&M 37 (23 Nov. 2012), Lot 21. | |
| 220. | A36 | P17 | 17.22 | ANS 1944.100.34381. | |
| 221.* | A46 | P18 | 17.20 | ANS 1944.100.34367. | |
| 2.2.3 <i>Ram-forepart r., two dots horizontally between struts, ΔA below. (Price -)</i> | | | | | |
| 222. | A18 | P1 | 17.37 | Adolph E. Cahn 68 (26 Nov. 1930) Lot 1234. | |
| 223. | A23 | P1 | 17.20 | Heritage (18 Apr. 2013), Lot 25730. | A23 worn |
| 224. | A28 | P2 | 17.25 | London, BM 1913,0518.12. | |
| 2.2.4 <i>Ram-forepart r., above strut dot, between struts dot, ΔA below. (Price 3205)</i> | | | | | |
| 225. | A11 | P1 | 17.08 | Lanz 151 (30 Jun. 2011) Lot 357. | |
| 226. | A18 | P2 | 17.08 | CNG, inventory no. 776703; CNG 72 (14 Jun. 2006), Lot 393. | |
| 227.* | A18 | P3 | 17.13 | ANS 1944.100.34379. | |
| 228. | A22 | P4 | 17.10 | ANS 1944.100.34363. | |
| 229. | A23 | P4 | 17.21 | HJB, inventory no. cc79789. | |
| 230. | A22 | P5 | 17.00 | CNG 41 (19 Mar. 1997), Lot 296. | |

231.	A26	P6	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34380.	
232.	A27	P6	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34368.	
233.	A27	P6	17.19	Bolaffi 29 (30 Nov 2016), Lot 36.	A27 advanced wear.
234.	A29	P7	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34369.	
235.	A29	P8	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34370.	
236.	A31	P9	17.06	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253156	
237.	A31	P10	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34372.	
238.	A33	P10	17.13	ANS 1944.100.34374.	
239.	A32	P11	17.26	Pars Coins VCoins Store G3917.	
240.	A33	P12	17.25	London, BM 1929,0811.72.	
241.	A33	P12	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34375.	
242.	A33	P13	17.13	Cambridge MA, Harvard Arts Museum.	
243.	A34	P14	17.02	CNG 49 (17 Mar. 1999), Lot 218; Glendining's (9 Oct. 1989), Lot 58.	ex Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664) per sale attribution.
244.	A34	P15	17.25	ANS 1944.100.34376.	
245.	A34	P15	17.25	ANS 1947.98.272.	
246.	A34	P15	17.22	Brüder Egger 40 (2 May 1912) Lot 674.	
247.	A35	P16	17.12	CNG 46 (24 Jun. 1998), Lot 179.	
248.	A36	P17	17.20	Adolph E. Cahn 61 (3 Dec. 1928), Lot 77.	
249.	A41	P18	17.23	Numismatik Naumann 49 (8 Jan. 2017), Lot 128.	

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| 250. | A41 | P19 | 15.91 | Manchester University Museum, SNG Vol. VII, 691. | A41 advanced die break on neck. |
| 251. | A47 | P19 | 17.19 | Cambridge MA, Harvard Arts Museum. | |
| 252. | A47 | P20 | 16.74 | Oxford, HCR23580; SNGuk_0503_2933. | Kuft Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1670). |
| 253. | A47 | P21 | 17.14 | CNG 47 (16 Sep. 1998), Lot 195. | |
| 254. | A47 | P22 | 17.15 | ANS 1944.100.34377. | |
| 255. | A47 | P23 | 17.16 | ANS 1944.100.34378. | |
| 256.* | A47 | P23 | 17.21 | ANS 1947.98.273. | |
| 257.* | A48 | P24 | 17.18 | Nomos 3 (10 May 2011), Lot 62. | |
| 258. | A48 | P24 | 17.22 | ANS 1944.100.34382. | |
| 259. | A49 | P25 | 17.25 | ANS 1944.100.34383. | |
| 260.* | A49 | P25 | 17.17 | ANS 1944.100.34384. | |
| 261. | A49 | P25 | 17.24 | ANS 1944.100.34509. | |
| 262. | A49 | P26 | 17.23 | ANS 1944.100.34510. | |
| 263.* | A50 | P27 | 17.25 | ANS 1944.100.34513. | |
| 264. | A51 | P27 | 17.22 | UBS Gold & Numismatics 52 (11 Sep. 2001), Lot 41. | |
| 265.* | A51 | P28 | 17.22 | ANS 1944.100.34514. | |
| 266* | A52 | P29 | 17.15 | Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253155. | |
| 2.2.5 <i>Ram-forepart r, between struts a dot, below strut a dot above ΔA.</i>
(Price -) | | | | | |
| 267. | A43 | P1 | 17.25 | Heritage (26 Apr. 2012), Lot 23075. | |
| 268. | A43 | P1 | 17.19 | Busso Peus Nachfolger 395 (May 2008), Lot 123. | |

269. A43 P2 17.23 ANS 1944.100.34526.
270. A43 P2 17.22 ANS 1963.117.1.
271. A49 P3 17.20 Wildwinds database
entry for Price 3205.
- 2.2.6 *Ram-forepart r., below throne struts dot, ΔA, dot. (Price 3206)*
- 272.* A43 P1 17.11 ANS 1944.100.34489.
273. A43 P2 17.22 ANS 1944.100.34511.
274. A43 P3 16.79 London, BM
1911,0409.32.
- 2.3.1 *Ram-forepart r., three dots horizontally above strut, ΔA below. (Price 3207)*
- 275.* A12 P1 17.26 ANS 1944.100.34532. Type 2 rev.
276. A12 P1 17.20 ANS 1944.100.34533. Type 2 rev.
277. A12 P2 17.25 Paris, BNF41771771;
1966.453.1005; SNG
Delepierre 1005. Type 2 rev.
278. A12 P3 17.21 ANS 1944.100.34534. Type 2 rev.
279. A14 P3 16.96 London, BM Type 2 rev.
RPK,p8oE.76.AleIII.
280. A13 P4 17.24 Berlin, Münzkabinett Type 2 rev.
18253158.
- 2.3.2 *Ram-forepart r., three dots in triangular disposition between struts, ΔA below. (Price -)*
281. A23 P1 17.30 Heritage 3040 (9 Apr.
2015), Lot 29044.
282. A32 P2 17.19 Eukratides A32 in earliest unworn
Numismatics Vcoins state.
Store (Sep 2016).
283. A32 P2 17.18 Kirk Davis VCoins P2 die breaking up
store. behind Zeus's raised
right arm and over
upper legend.

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| 284. | A47 | P3 | 17.20 | Naville I (4 Apr. 1921), Lot 918; ex Pozzi Coll. | A47 large die break above head. |
| 285. | A52 | P3 | 17.07 | Naville I (4 Apr. 1921), Lot 917; ex Pozzi Coll. | |
| 2.3.3 | <i>Ram-forepart r., one dot above strut, two dots horizontally between struts, ΔA below. (Price -)</i> | | | | |
| 286. | A31 | P1 | 17.23 | London, BM 1929,0811.76. | A31 in early state. |
| 2.3.4 | <i>Ram-forepart r., two dots vertically above strut, one dot above ΔA below. (Price -)</i> | | | | |
| 287. | A13 | P1 | 17.25 | London, BM 929,0811.74. | Type 2 rev. |
| 288. | A13 | P2 | 17.21 | London, BM 1913,0518.1. | Type 2 rev. |
| 289. | A13 | P3 | 17.24 | Baldwins 68 (28 Sep. 2010), Lot 3391. | Type 2 rev. |
| 2.3.5 | <i>Ram-forepart r., above strut, two dots, below ΔA above one dot. (Price -)</i> | | | | |
| 290. | A12 | P1 | 17.18 | CNG 35 (20 Sep. 1995), Lot 119. | Type 2 rev. |
| 291. | A13 | P2 | 17.16 | CNG 45 (18 Mar. 1998), Lot 203. | Type 2 rev. |
| 292. | A13 | P2 | 17.18 | CNG, inventory no. 778082. | Type 2 rev. |

2.3.6 *Ram-forepart r., above strut, dot, between strut, dot, below strut dot above ΔA. (Price 3208)*

293.	A11	P1	17.20	London, BM 1987,0649.468.
294.	A11	P1	17.08	Künker 168 (12 Mar. 2010), Lot 7241.
295.	A11	P1	17.10	Paris, BNF41771768; 1966.453.1002; SNG Delepierre 1002.
296.	A11	P2	17.24	ANS 1944.100.34529.
297.	A11	P3	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34530.
298.	A11	P3	17.00	CNG eAuction 164 (9 May 2007), Lot 46; CNG eAuction 137 (12 Apr. 2006), Lot 4.
299.	A15	P4	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34407.
300.	A15	P5	17.14	ANS 1944.100.34408.
301.	A17	P6	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34386.
302.	A17	P7	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34387.
303.	A18	P8	17.20	CNG, inventory no. 776704; CNG 72 (14 Jun. 2006), Lot 394.
304.	A18	P8	17.21	CNG 36 (5–6 Dec.1995) Lot 1827.
305.	A18	P9	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34404.
306.	A18	P9	16.29	Aegean Numismatics VCoins store, inventory no. 030626.
307.	A18	P9	16.89	Baldwin's 83 (24 Sep. 2013), Lot 4033a.
308.	A18	P10	16.89	Naumann, Auction 46 (11 Sep. 2016) Lot 120; Dorotheum (18 May 2016), Lot 664.

309.	A18	P11	17.15	Triton X CNG 74 (8 Jan. 2007), Lot 155.	
310.	A22	P12	17.09	CNG eAuction 356 (29 Jul. 2015), Lot 24.	
311.	A23	P13	16.89	ANS 1974.26.568.	
312.	A24	P14	17.22	The New York Sale Auction XXIII (6 Jan. 2010), Lot 16.	
313.	A24	P14	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34390.	
314.	A24	P15	17.15	ANS 1944.100.34391.	
315.	A24	P15	17.15	Münzhandlung Ritter GmbH, inventory no. 40492.	A24 well worn.
316.	A25	P16	17.20	G&M 160 (9 Oct. 2007), Lot 1317.	A25 early die break on neck.
317.	A25	P17	17.10	Savoca Numismatik 12 (22 Jan. 2017), Lot 130.	
318.	A25	P17	17.15	ANS 1944.100.34393.	P17 die fragmented on ram's head.
319.	A28	P18	17.27	Ancient Numismatic Enterprise VCoins store, inventory no. 3152.	
320.	A28	P19	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34400.	
321.	A28	P20	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34401.	
322.	A28	P21	17.21	HJB, inventory no. cc72134 .	
323.	A28	P22	17.08	Oxford, HCR23581; SNGuk_0503_2934.	
324.	A28	P23	17.26	ANS 1944.100.34399.	
325.	A47	P23	17.04	ANS 1974.26.569.	A47 early die breaks. P23 fragment missing on and below eagle's tail and hand of Zeus.

326.	A47	P24	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34402.	A47 with advanced die breaks on lion scalp and above head.
327.	A35	P25	17.14	Künker 89 (8 Mar. 2004), Lot 1202.	
328.	A35	P25	17.24	ANS 1944.100.34405.	
329.	A47	P25	17.08	ANS 1944.100.34403.	A47 with advanced die breaks on lion scalp and above head.
330.	A48	P25	17.29	ANS 1944.100.34410.	
331.	A35	P26	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34406.	
332.*	A53	P26	16.99	Paris, BNF41838015.	A53 with large fragment of die missing before ear.
333.	A38	P27	17.10	ANS 1961.37.3	A38 extensive die breaks.
334.	A42	P27	17.26	London, BM 1912,0905.28.	Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664).
335.	A42	P27	17.24	ANS 1944.100.34522.	
336.	A43	P28	17.22	ANS 1947.98.278.	
337.	A43	P28	17.24	London, BM 2002,0101.723.	
338.	A43	P28	17.21	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253157.	
339.	A44	P29	16.98	ANS 1944.100.34528.	
340.	A46	P30	17.29	London, BM 1908,0110.2351.	
341.	A46	P31	17.22	CNG eAuction 252 (23 Mar. 2011), Lot 31.	
342.	A46	P31	17.23	G&M 186 (8 Mar. 2010), Lot 1259.	
343.	A46	P32	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34394.	
344.	A46	P32	17.14	ANS 1944.100.34396.	

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| 345. | A46 | P32 | 17.07 | ANS 1944.100.34397. | P32 breaking into fragments. |
| 346. | A48 | P33 | 17.24 | ANS 1944.100.34413. | A48 die break above head. |
| 347. | A48 | P33 | 17.25 | ANS 1944.100.34414. | |
| 348. | A48 | P34 | 17.24 | Manchester University Museum, SNG Vol. VII, 692; Glendining (3 May 1929), Lot 444. | A48 large die break above head—die fragmenting. |
| 349. | A49 | P35 | 17.20 | ANS 1944.100.34523. | |
| 350. | A49 | P36 | 17.13 | HJB, inventory no. cc86335; HJB 197 (27 Apr. 2016), Lot 58. | |
| 351. | A49 | P36 | 17.15 | G&M 170 (13 Oct. 2008), Lot 1255. | |
| 352. | A49 | P36 | 15.50 | ANS 1944.100.34525. | Abu Hommos Hoard (IGCH 1667). |
| 353. | A49 | P37 | 17.22 | ANS 1944.100.34524. | |
| 354.* | A54 | P38 | 17.24 | ANS 1944.100.34527. | |
| 2.3.7 <i>Ram-forepart r., three dots vertically, between struts, ΔA below. (Price -)</i> | | | | | |
| 355. | A18 | P1 | 16.95 | Naumann 41 (6 Mar. 2016), Lot 117. | |
| 356. | A23 | P1 | 17.27 | London, BM 1929,0811.73. | A23 very worn. |
| 357. | A18 | P2 | 16.77 | London, BM G.2605. | A18 very worn. |
| 358. | A41 | P3 | 17.18 | London, BM 1913,0518.2 | Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664). |
| 2.4.1 <i>Ram-forepart r., above strut, two dots, below strut ΔA above two dots. (Price 3209)</i> | | | | | |
| 359. | A14 | P1 | 17.25 | CNG, inventory no. 819915. | Type 2 rev. |
| 360. | A14 | P1 | 17.21 | ANS 1944.100.34545. | Type 2 rev. |

361.	A14	P1	17.27	London, BM 2002,0101.724.	Type 2 rev.
2.4.2 <i>Ram-forepart r., four dots between struts, ΔA below. (Price 3210)</i>					
362.	A16	P1	17.15	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253129.	
363.	A16	P1	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34438.	
364.	A16	P1	17.06	ANS 1944.100.34439.	A16 well worn.
365.	A17	P2	17.13	ANS 1944.100.34419.	
366.	A17	P3	16.60	CNG eAuction 352 (3 Jun. 2015), Lot 67.	
367.	A17	P3	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34420.	A17 with advanced wear.
368.	A18	P4	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34441.	
369.	A18	P4	17.24	Paris, BNF41771769; 1966.453.1003; SNG Delepierre 1003.	
370.	A19	P5	17.13	Blackburn Museum, SNG Vol. III, 474; SNGuk_0800_0474.	
371.	A20	P6	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34415.	
372.	A20	P7	17.11	ANS 1944.100.34416.	A20 die break on cheek and below neck truncation.
373.	A20	P8	17.21	G&M 156 (5 Mar. 2007), Lot 1276.	A20 more extensive die breaks
374.	A20	P9	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34417.	A20 very worn and broken.
375.	A23	P10	17.16	CNG 97 (17 Sep. 2014), Lot 87.	
376.	A23	P11	16.98	London, BM 1866,1201.1076.	A23 worn.
377.	A23	P12	16.61	London, BM 1908,0110.2350.	A23 worn.

378.	A24	P13	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34421.	A24 early die break at base of mane.
379.	A24	P14	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34449.	
380.	A25	P15	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34422.	
381.	A25	P16	17.18	ANS 1944.100.34423.	
382.	A25	P17	17.09	G&M 181 (13 Oct. 2009), Lot 1306.	
383.	A26	P18	17.20	Aegean Numismatics 060602.	
384.	A26	P18	17.14	ANS 1944.100.34424.	
385.	A26	P19	17.16	Heritage (16 Aug. 2010), Lot 21998.	
386.	A26	P20	16.97	Paris, BNF41848497.	
387.	A27	P21	17.19	London, BM 2002,0101.725.	
388.	A27	P22	17.10	ANS 1944.100.34425.	
389.	A27	P22	16.96	Cambridge, Ma., Harvard Art Museum.	A27 in most worn state.
390.	A28	P23	17.25	ANS 1944.100.34426.	P23 four coalesced dots appear as two.
391.	A28	P23	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34427.	Abu Hommos Hoard. P23 four coalesced dots appear as two.
392.	A28	P24	17.19	G&M 121 (10 Mar. 2003), Lot 86.	
393.	A29	P25	17.26	London, BM 1929,0811.75.	A29 early state.
394.	A29	P25	16.13	ANS 1944.100.34429.	
395.	A29	P26	17.25	ANS 1944.100.34430.	
396.	A29	P27	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34431.	
397.	A29	P28	17.00	ANS 1944.100.34432.	

398.	A31	P28	16.77	Heidelberger Münzhandlung Herbert Grün 54 (16 Nov. 2010), Lot 31.	
399.	A31	P29	17.08	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253159.	
400.	A31	P30	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34433.	
401.	A31	P31	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34434.	
402.	A32	P32	17.05	Oxford, HCR23582; SNGuk_0503_2935.	Kuft Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1670).
403.	A32	P32	17.18	Stack's (15 Jan. 2007), Lot 4048.	
404.	A32	P32	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34435.	
405.	A32	P33	17.16	ANS 1944.100.34436.	A32 large fragment dislodged from circumference 4h–7h (on coin).
406.	A32	P33	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34437.	A32 well worn.
407.	A33	P34	17.18	eBay axismundi.com.	
408.	A33	P34	17.21	Lanz 102 (28 May 2001), Lot 189.	
409.	A34	P35	17.21	ANS 1944.100.34428.	
410.	A34	P36	16.90	ANS 1944.100.34440	Abu Hommos Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1667).
411.	A35	P37	17.11	NAC 78 (26 May 2014), Lot 1401.	
412.	A36	P38	17.26	ANS 1944.100.34442.	
413.	A36	P38	17.10	London, BM 1878,0301.117.	
414.	A36	P38	17.14	ANS 1944.100.34443.	
415.	A38	P38	17.24	ANS 1944.100.34444.	A38 breaking up on lion paws tie.
416.	A38	P38	17.19	ANS 1944.100.34445.	A38 breaking up on lion paws tie.
417.	A39	P38	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34446.	

418. A41 P39 16.22 ANS 1944.100.34447. A41 worn with developing die breaks.
419. A47 P40 17.22 ANS 1947.98.274.
420. A47 P40 16.95 Kirk Davis VCoins store. A47 worn with die breaks on lion skin.
421. A48 P41 17.20 ANS 1944.100.34448.
422. A49 P42 17.04 CNG eAuction 263 (31 Aug. 2011), Lot 34.
- 2.4.3 *Above strut, four dots—missing ram-forepart and ΔA. (Price -)*
- 423.* A20 P1 17.13 ANS 1944.100.34418. P1 without ram forepart and missing ΔA. A20 very worn with extensive die breaks.
- 2.5.1 *Ram-forepart r., five dots between struts, below strut ΔA. (Price 3211)*
424. A17 P1 17.03 Baldwin's 68 (28 Sep 2010), Lot 3299. A17 worn.
425. A24 P2 14.91 ANS 1944.100.34450. A24 well worn.
426. A24 P2 17.16 Paris, BNF 41771770; 1966.453.1004; SNG Delepierre 1004. A24 well worn.
427. A25 P3 17.08 ANS 1944.100.34451. A25 with die breaks.
428. A25 P4 17.01 Nauman 21 (7 Sep. 2014), Lot 120. A25 most advanced wear with die breaks.
- 429.* A28 P5 17.10 ANS 1944.100.34452.
430. A28 P5 17.21 CNG, inventory no. 862652; CNG 91 (19 Sep. 2012), Lot 130; Heritage (3 June 2005), Lot 12023. A28 with advanced die break on lion scalp above Herakles ear.

431.	A29	P6	17.22	Oxford, Ashmolean Museum, <i>SNG</i> Vol. III, 1451; <i>SN-Guk_0300_1451</i> ; Lockett Collection; Naville 6 (28 Nov. 1924), Lot 741.	A29 worn with prominent die breaks on upper cheek and in lion's mane.
432.	A29	P6	17.04	Münzenkontor Kornblum MA-ID 16082900400312.	A29 die breaks in mane and on cheek.
433.	A31	P7	17.17	ANS 1944.100.34453.	
434.	A31	P8	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34454.	
435.	A31	P8	16.95	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253160.	
436.*	A31	P9	17.21	Oxford, HCR23583; <i>SNGuk_0503_2936</i> .	Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1664).
437.	A31	P9	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34455.	
438.	A33	P10	17.22	ANS 1944.100.34457.	
439.	A33	P10	17.03	Paris, BNF41747235; de Luynes 1632.	
440.	A34	P11	17.23	London, BM 2002,0101.726	
441.	A34	P12	17.12	UBS Gold & Numismatics 76 (22 Jan. 2008), Lot 1254.	
442.	A34	P12	17.23	ANS 1944.100.34462.	
443.	A34	P12	17.20	ANS 1944.100.34456.	

2.5.2 *five dots, ΔA. Ram-forepart absent. (Price 3213 corr.)*

No examples recorded in PELLA or commerce. One example reported by Newell (1923) but no image available—Newell Demanhur 3246. The location of this coin is unknown.

2.6.1 *Ram-forepart r., six dots between struts, ΔA below. (Price 3212)*

- | | | | | | |
|-------|-----|----|-------|---|--|
| 444. | A25 | P1 | 16.74 | Zlotnik (2010), <i>INR</i>
5, pp. 31–40, 16. | Reverse described as
bearing six globules—
image unclear. A25 most
advanced wear. |
| 445. | A39 | P2 | 17.18 | ANS 1944.100.34459. | A39 advanced wear. |
| 446.* | A41 | P3 | 17.21 | ANS 1944.100.34463. | A41 with most advanced
wear. |

2.6.2 *Ram-forepart r., above top strut dot, between strut five coalesced dots giving the illusion of the letter A, below strut ΔA. (Price 3214)*

- | | | | | | |
|-------|-----|----|-------|--|--|
| 447. | A29 | P1 | 17.10 | The New York Sale
XXIII (6 Jan. 2010),
Lot 17. | |
| 448.* | A29 | P1 | 17.22 | London, BM
1929,0811.77. | Demanhur Hoard (<i>IGCH</i>
1664). A29 die break
advancing from hairline
into cheek. Breaks in
mane. High die wear. |

2.7.1 *Ram-forepart r., below throne struts ivy leaf above ΔA. (Price 3215)*

- | | | | | | |
|-------|-----|----|-------|-----------------------------------|---|
| 449.* | A42 | P1 | 17.21 | London, BM
1881,0102.38. | |
| 450. | A42 | P2 | 16.45 | ANS 1944.100.34541. | |
| 451. | A42 | P3 | 17.20 | ANS 1944.100.34542. | A42 worn with small
developing breaks. |
| 452.* | A43 | P4 | 17.23 | ANS 1947.98.280. | |
| 453. | A43 | P4 | 17.22 | London, BM
1912,0905.29. | Demanhur Hoard
(<i>IGCH</i> 1664). |
| 454. | A43 | P4 | 17.02 | Berlin, Münzkabinett
18253162. | |
| 455. | A44 | P5 | 17.25 | ANS 1944.100.34544. | A44 worn. |
| 456. | A44 | P5 | 16.72 | London, BM
1913,0518.4. | Demanhur Hoard
(<i>IGCH</i> 1664). A44
worn. |

COMMENTARY

The most salient aspect to come from the catalogue is that after an initial phase of serial striking of each of Series 1 and Series 2 the mint produced its coinage in a complexly interwoven, obverse die linked manner, indicative of substantial parallel striking. At its peak, this involved six striking teams and anvils (Table 1, below).

Twelve percent of the catalogue entries define 30 pairs of obverse dies linked by a shared reverse die, all but three of which occur within the issues bearing secondary mint controls in the form of sequences of dots beneath the *diphros* (Table 2, below). These reverse die links associate 30 obverse dies with one or more other obverse dies during the mintage. They occur in a multiplicity of sequence types and involve more than half of the obverse dies in the catalogue. This serves to emphasise that there is no relative chronological significance in the sequence types defined by specific arrangement, or placement of dots and that the obverse dies involved are broadly contemporaneous with each other, i.e. there was no extended period of striking over many years.

Series 1

Characterized by the presence of the vertically oriented $\mathcal{A}X$ mint control on the left field reverse, Series 1 is represented by 41 coins and five discrete sequence types in the catalogue. Coins in this series bear zero-, one-, two-, four-, or five - dot secondary controls on the reverse, beneath the *diphros* upon which is seated Zeus.

In the catalogue of Series 1, four obverse and sixteen reverse dies are identified. The first two obverse dies in the sequence (A1 and A2) are associated exclusively with Type 1.0.1 (Cat. Nos. 1–16), which carries no secondary mint control. These dies were used sequentially to strike this type in a serial manner on a single anvil. In contrast, dies A3 and A4 are associated with a number of dot control bearing issues (Cat. Nos. 17–41) struck in an interwoven manner suggestive of parallel striking.

Shortly after the introduction of the dot form secondary mint controls, obverse die A3 was used to strike an example of 2.1.1 (Cat. No. 100; Pl. 8, 100) thus linking the two series. The progression of die wear on A3 indicates that the Series 2 coin was struck before the last of the Series 1 coins from this die (Cat. Nos. 40–41). This obverse die link provides a chronological peg tying together Series 1 and 2. It indicates that the Series 1 mintage with dot controls was synchronous with the initial employment of dot controls in Series 2. This obverse die link between Series 1 and Series 2 was unknown previously.

Series 2 (continued)	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54
-																								
One dot	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x									
Two dots	x	x	x	x	x	x					x		x			x	x	x	x	x	x			
Three dots	x	x			x			x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x
Four dots	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x						x	x	x					
Five dots	x		x	x																				
Six dots									x		x													
Ivy Leaf												x	x	x										

Table 1 (continued). Obverse die use by dot control sequence.

Table 2. Reverse die links.

Obverse dies linked by a shared reverse die		Cat. Nos.	Secondary control
A4	A3	22-23	-
A3	A4	24-28	-
A8	A9	52-53	-
A17	A18	123-124	one dot
A24	A25	148-149	one dot
A29	A30	160-161	one dot
A29	A31	160-162	one dot
A30	A31	161-162	one dot
A34	A35	168-169	one dot
A22	A23	215-216	two dots
A23	A25	216-217	two dots
A22	A25	215-217	two dots
A18	A23	222-223	two dots
A22	A23	228-229	two dots
A26	A27	231-232	two dots
A31	A33	237-238	two dots
A41	A47	250-251	two dots
A50	A51	263-264	two dots
A47	A52	284-285	three dots
A28	A47	324-325	three dots
A35	A47	328-329	three dots
A47	A48	329-330	three dots
A35	A48	328-330	three dots
A35	A53	331-332	three dots
A38	A42	333-334	three dots
A18	A23	355-356	three dots
A29	A31	397-398	four dots
A36	A38	414-415	four dots
A38	A39	416-417	four dots
A36	A39	414-417	four dots

Series 2

Represented by 415 coins in the catalogue, Series 2 is larger and more diverse than Series 1. In place of the $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{X}$ mint control of Series 1 is the forepart of a ram (Pls. 7–13, 42–452), found on all but three specimens. The first of these three seemingly anomalous coins is the sole known example of 2.0.2 (Cat. No. 116). No mint controls are present on this coin. Its attribution to Damaskos is established by the fact that obverse die A17 from which it was struck links it to a number other types in Series 2. Similarly missing both primary controls is the sole representative of 2.4.3 (Cat. No. 423) linked by obverse die A20 to other sequence types in the catalogue. Although not represented in the catalogue by a coin, type 2.5.2, which is absent the ram-forepart, is known from Newell's description of a specimen (Demanhur 3246) from the Demanhur Hoard (*IGCH* 1664).⁸ The whereabouts of the coin is unknown, so that the obverse die from which it was struck is indeterminate. In the case of the first two coins no corrected, completely engraved, otherwise identical reverse could be identified in the catalogue. In all three cases, they are known from a solitary example, so that we have little basis for discriminating whether their origin was the result of an accidental, or deliberate engraving omission. The fact that these coins passed through the mint's control process into circulation, suggests that the secondary controls they carried (zero, four, and five dots respectively) were adequate to fulfil the mint's internal controls process requirement (see Mint Controls below).

Fifty-one obverse and 284 reverse dies are represented in Series 2. The first five dies of Series 2 (A5–A9) were used to strike coinage in a serial manner, as occurred with the first two obverse dies of Series 1. After this brief episode of serial striking there is an explosion of dot control types struck in an interwoven, obverse die linked manner, detailed in the catalogue and summarized in Table 1. This pattern of obverse die usage is not amenable to presentation in a catalogue laid out in a serial manner, so that the catalogue belies the true complexity of the Series 2 emission. To detail the nuances in the progression of wear on many obverse dies would require the division of each sequence type into a multitude of entries interwoven with that of other sequence types using the same obverse dies. The catalogue would prove difficult to read, almost incomprehensible in this detail. Catalogue notes on the wear state of dies for various entries shed some light on this complexity.

Based on the interwoven, obverse die-linked coinage (Table 1) struck from dies A10–A54 it is apparent that these obverse dies constituted a shared die

8. Newell, *Alexander*, 49.

inventory for the striking of the multitude of dot-bearing mint control types. Forty-one obverse dies, representing 80 percent of Series 2 dies, were used to strike sequence type 2.0.1 (no dot control) plus 2.1.1 (single-dot control). Of those 31 were also used to strike other types. Types 2.0.1 and 2.1.1 represent the core of Series 2, with other types, bearing multiple dot controls, produced in parallel, drawing upon the same obverse dies as those used to strike the core issues. It is notable that type 2.0.1 ceased production after A17 was commissioned, so that from this point on, roughly one third of the way through the life of the mint based on obverse die count, all the output bore some form of secondary mint control, principally a dot pattern. Only after the cessation of 2.0.1 (no dot control) did the six dot mint control (2.6.1–2.6.2; Cat. Nos. 444–448) make its appearance in the sequence. Similarly it was only after the cessation of the six dot secondary control (2.6.1–2.6.2) that the ivy leaf symbol appeared.

With regard to these dot form secondary controls, sequence type 2.6.2 requires comment. This type was categorized previously as Price 3214 bearing a single dot above the topmost strut of the *diphros*, while carrying the letter A between the struts. It is known from two examples (Cat. Nos. 447–448), each struck from the same die pair, A29/P1. Detailed examination of the reverse of the two coins reveals that the A is in fact an illusion, the result of the coalescence of five dots arranged in a triangular or Λ pattern. In the closely spaced middle row of two dots, the dots have merged to give the impression of the horizontal bar of the letter A. Thus, Price 3214 is an ambiguity of a six-dot control, where the sixth dot was placed above the topmost strut of the *diphros*, while below the five close spaced, coalesced dots were misread as the letter A. When compiling the catalogue a similar difficulty was experienced in accurately reading some of the examples of the five-dot control type 2.5.1, dependent on the quality and care with which the dots were engraved.

The sole departure from the dot-based secondary controls occurs with sequence type 2.7.1 (Cat. Nos. 449–456) This type from three obverse and five reverse dies is characterized by the introduction of a symbol control, an ivy leaf, immediately above the ΔA ethnic. The possible significance of this control is discussed below.

MINT CONTROLS

The interpretation of Hellenistic mint controls consisting of letters, monograms, symbols and even dot controls is an often contentious subject, with the various alternative interpretations summarized by Callataÿ who wrote “Not all these explanations are convincing, and several appear very unlikely or exceptional

(magistrates, liturgists, engravers, military officers or units). The marks are best viewed as internal control marks, whose number and efficiency have to be considered in their broader archival context.⁹ In this conclusion, Callataÿ provides a framework for consideration of the primary and secondary mint controls on the coinage of Damaskos.

Firstly, the ΔA control readily resolves as the abbreviated name of the city, identifying the issuing mint. This practice finds a direct parallel in the contemporary Alexander coinage from Myriandros (Μ), Arados (Α), Arados II (Α), Karne (Κ), Berytos (Β) and Sidon (ΣΙ), each of which carries an abbreviated letter form, or monogram, of the city's name. Conventionally, the ΑΧ and ram-forepart controls would be associated with the 'magistrates' responsible for the oversight of the production of Series 1 and Series 2 respectively. It is equally possible that they could have served to identify the two workshops, or even anvils, from which each series initially originated. In this possibility, the writer is inclined to speculate that the Α component of the ΑΧ control may reflect the origin from Arados of some of the experienced mint workers engaged to open the mint. However, as we have no means of testing this speculation, the writer simply notes it as an intriguing possibility. After the first two obverse and six reverse dies, it appears that the Series 1 (ΑΧ) workshop was consolidated into the Series 2 (ram-forepart) facility during the transition from the serial striking of coinage at each to substantial parallel striking in a single facility under one primary control. This process of consolidation saw the last two obverse dies of Series 1 paired to 10 reverse dies bearing dot controls in addition to the ΑΧ mint control, after which the latter was dropped completely. No matter what the interpretation of the significance of each of the ΑΧ and ram-forepart mint controls, be they the identification of 'magistrates' or separate 'workshops,' it was the ram-forepart that continued for the duration of the Damaskos mintage, while the ΑΧ mint control was discontinued after less than 20 percent of the mint's output had been struck.

To infer the possible significance of the dot controls requires consideration of Callataÿ's "broader archival context" of their development and implementation. The first step for establishing the broader archival context is the die study.

Table 1 summarizes the many obverse die links between the various secondary control sequences that are characterized by a number of dots, or in one instance a symbol. The most striking aspect of this is that after a brief sequence of

9. F. de Callataÿ, "Quantifying Monetary Production in Greco-Roman Times: A General Frame," in *Quantifying Monetary Supplies in Greco-Roman Times*, ed. F. de Callataÿ (Bari: Edipuglia), 39–62.

serial die usage in each of Series 1 (involving A1–A2) and Series 2 (involving A5–A9), a complexly interlinked pattern of die use develops. The tightly knit, interlinking of obverse dies is characteristic of multi-anvil operation drawing upon a shared inventory of obverse dies. It is indicative of a high volume coinage produced over a relatively short period of time. One obverse die (A23) is associated with seven different types of dot control patterns, while paired with 13 reverse dies, indicative of the extensive parallel striking of the dot control sequences.

Linking Series 1 to Series 2, die A3 provides a chronological peg for the relative sequencing of the two series. The commissioning of this die was coincident with the start of parallel striking in both series of a complexly die linked, interwoven number of issues in both series bearing the inconspicuous dot controls. This establishes that the prior initial serial striking of each of Series 1 and Series 2 was contemporaneous,¹⁰ representing the opening stage of the mint, during which time it appears that two separate workshops were in operation, each characterized by their discrete reverse left field mint controls. With the commencement of parallel striking in both series, the two-workshop separation was abandoned; quickly leading to the cessation of Series 1 coinage within the remaining life of dies A3 and A4. In effect, the *R*X workshop was consolidated into the ram-forepart workshop during the implementation of a parallel striking process built around six anvils. Based on the obverse die count, this consolidation occurred in the first fifth of the mint's life.

From this we can infer that after a brief commissioning period, characterized by the serial striking of the earliest of each of Series 1 and Series 2, the mint was expanded to achieve a higher production rate through the employment of numerous striking teams and anvils, while utilizing the obverse dies as shared inventory among the various striking teams (Table 1). At this stage, the obverse dies came to be paired with reverse dies bearing the many and varied secondary control dot sequences. The dot controls are relatively inconspicuous and in this sense plausibly served to facilitate internal control processes in the mint. Within this framework a possible explanation of the many dot control sequences is that they served to identify on a daily basis the output from each of the anvils, or individual striking teams, that operated in the mint. The number of dots, rather than their placement, is the most salient aspect, indicating that six anvils were used to strike the coinage following the consolidation of mint operations under the ram-forepart control. This interpretation is consistent with the pattern of extensive

10. Based on the obverse die count in the serially struck coinage of each series, it is possible that Series 1 (dies A1–A2) started a little later than Series 2 (dies A5–A9).

obverse die linkages noted in Table 1. At any one time six obverse dies were utilized simultaneously, on a rolling basis, each paired to a different reverse die type (dot control sequence) that was specific to the anvil on which the obverse die was used, the latter varying from one day to the next. In effect, the obverse dies were used as a shared die inventory by the striking teams.

The daily process of reconciliation of the silver provided to each striking team with the coinage struck by each team was facilitated by individually identifying with a unique number of dots the coinage struck on each of six anvils. The development of this process control mechanism had the advantage of minimizing the requirement for physical oversight of each striking team in its daily work, enabling multiple teams to work under one roof within the framework of a robust accounting and reconciliation process that was capable of identifying malfeasance within any individual striking team.

With an increasing number of small, closely engraved dots on a die, the potential for ambiguity in the reading of the number of dots on a coin struck from it increases. This potential for ambiguity depends on the precision with which the dots were engraved and their arrangement on the die. Type 2.6.2 is an example in a modern-day context of this potential for ambiguity. On this type the engraving of five closely-spaced dots between the struts was read as the letter A in prior studies, when in fact the A is nothing more than a coalesced pattern of five dots. The difficulty and potential ambiguity in reading a large number of small closely spaced dots amongst the dotted elements comprising the struts of the *diphros* may have prompted the adoption of a symbol for a secondary control in place of the dot sequence controls on sequence type 2.7.1. Supporting this possibility is the fact that the symbol control appears in the catalogue sequence after the last of the six-dot controls.

In the context of the interpretation of the significance of the dot controls the three anomalous sequence types noted previously, 2.0.2 (no controls), 2.4.3 (four dots, no primary controls) and 2.5.2 (five dots, plus ΔA primary control only), potentially illustrate the primary focus of the mint's control processes. These types are each derived from a single reverse die. Although representing only 0.4% (4,500 coins in 1.22 million coins struck—see Size and Duration of the Emission section below) of the mint's output, these coins passed into circulation, despite either the absence (2.0.2 and 2.4.3), or incomplete nature (2.5.2), of the primary controls. They may have been the result of die engraving omissions, yet they passed through the mint's control processes into circulation. Why? Potentially because the secondary controls they bore (zero, four, and five dots) were sufficient to fulfil the internal accounting and reconciliation control processes

in the mint, a function in which the primary controls played no part. If so, this indicates that the primary focus of the mint in its objective of producing a large volume of coinage in a short time, was the integrity of its internal control process involving the accounting for and reconciliation of silver input and coinage output. Under the pressure to produce a high volume of coinage on six anvils, the absence of incomplete primary controls on a few coins was insufficient to warrant restriking of the coins, provided the secondary controls they bore fulfilled the mint's internal control processes.

Alternative explanations of these inconspicuous dot controls include the identification of mint officials or 'magistrates' and more recently the recipients of the coinage.¹¹ In the author's opinion these interpretations are less compelling in the broad archival context than the interpretation that these inconspicuous dots were used as a means of facilitating the mint's internal control process. The latter must have involved the daily accounting for and reconciliation of silver input and struck coinage output in a production operation consisting of a large number of striking teams/anvils within a single secure facility.

ICONOGRAPHY AND STYLE

Although subjective in its assessment, the work of up to nine die engravers can be recognized in the dies identified in the catalogue of coins (Table 3). Four engravers were engaged at the opening of the mint, the initial stage of which involved the serial striking of each of Series 1 and Series 2 in parallel with each other. Engravers 1 and 2 were responsible for the Series 1 dies A1–A4, while engravers 3 and 4 were responsible for dies A5–A9. The obverse and reverse style of Series 1 and Series 2 at this stage of the mint's life is uniform and undifferentiated between the series. It has some affinity with that of the earliest issues of the northern Phoenician and Syrian mints, in turn a derivative of the Tarsos mint established a few years earlier. In general terms, the style appears as a derivative, via an amalgam of various style elements found on some of the earliest Alexanders of Arados. This derivative style involves the portrayal of Herakles with a somewhat angular form of lion skin headdress, accompanied on the reverse by a rigid, highly stylized portrayal of Zeus with parallel legs. In detail, the lion skin headdress worn by Herakles has a distinctively double, rather than multiply creased form at the base of the neck into the lion-paw tie. The mane possesses outward projecting tufts, rather than a more downward directed mane (compare these style elements on Series 1 dies A1–A2, Pl. 6, 1–5 to Pl. 14, D–F;

11. Brad Nelson, personal communication via Dr. Ute Wartenberg Kagan, May 26, 2017.

Duyrat Groups I–III).¹² This distinctive amalgam of stylistic attributes evident in the earliest Damaskos dies, suggest the possibility that the dies from which the earliest Series I and 2 coinage derived might have been produced by engravers mobilized from one of the regional mints of the littoral eastern Mediterranean, with Arados a possibility.

Table 3. Die engravers.

Engraver	Obverse die
1	1, 2
2	3, 4, 15, 24, 26, 28, 29, 30 31, 47, 48
3	5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 23
4	9, 39, 40, 42, 49
5	11, 12, 13, 14, 44, 50, 51, 54
6	16, 19, 20, 22, 25, 27, 32
7	17, 18, 21, 35, 36, 37, 38, 41, 46, 52, 53
8	33, 34
9	43, 45

The expansion of the mint to six anvils was associated with an increase in the number of die engravers engaged at the mint (Table 3). This was necessary to meet the demand for dies from up to six striking teams working in parallel. It resulted in an increased diversity of style in the later Series 2 dies, possibly reflecting the origin of at least three engravers (engravers 5, 8, and 9) from beyond the region of northern Phoenicia, Syria and Kilikia. The style of engraver 5 is notable for the depiction of Herakles with a large more rounded and fluid form than is the norm on other dies. The first four obverse dies from this engraver (A11–A14) were paired almost exclusively to a succession of reverse dies of unique style, not just in the Damaskos series but also in all the mints of the east. This style portrays Zeus with a semi-frontal style, seated on a *diphros* braced by a single strut, accompanied by a foreshortening of the footstool in an attempt to provide perspective (e.g. Cat Nos. 72–96, Pls. 7–8, 72–84). This style of reverse is noted as “Type 2 rev.” in the catalogue and is represented by 43 of 298 reverse dies. It most resembles some of the ‘Alexander’ drachm issues of Sardis

12. Plate images of Arados tetradrachms: D = ANS 1944.100.34562 (Price 3303), E = ANS 1944.100.34569 (Price 3305) and F = ANS 1944.100.34571 (Price 3305). Refer also to F. Duyrat, *Arados hellénistique étude historique et monétaire* (Beirut: Institut Français du Proche-Orient, 2005), 14 and pl. 1, 4–33.

(Pl. 14, G)¹³ in the period 325–323 BC. However, this newly introduced style was short-lived. A11 in the last stages of its use (Cat Nos. 293–298) as well as the later obverse dies from the hand of engraver 5 (A44, A50, A51 and A54) are paired to reverse dies in the more conventional derivative regional style (Pl. 12, 263–265 and Pl. 13, 354) that accounts for more than 85 percent of reverse dies in the catalogue. Based on these observations it is possible that engraver 5 may have come from as far afield as Asia Minor to meet the increased resource requirements of the mint.¹⁴

Beyond the influences on style resultant from the introduction of new engravers at the mint, there is one notable change in an element of the iconography of the reverse dies that appears to be deliberate and has chronological significance. This involves the portrayal of the outstretched right hand of Zeus upon which is perched his eagle. On a sole example (Cat. No. 1; Pl. 6, 1) of the earliest reverse die of the mint, the right hand of Zeus is portrayed crudely with a facing open palm and splayed fingers (detail shown on Pl. 14, A). This is consistent with the representation on the earliest lifetime Alexander issues of the eastern mints that commenced production immediately after each fell under Alexander's rule. However, on the second reverse die (Cat. No. 2; Pl. 6, 2) and on all subsequent reverse dies, this portrayal is changed to one in which the outstretched hand is displayed in profile, oriented upward, often in a cupped or semi-closed manner beneath the eagle. The progression of this change across the first three reverse dies is illustrated in detail on Plate 14, A–C. This change in portrayal of the right hand of Zeus occurred in all the eastern mints that commenced operation before 325 (Table 4). Mints that opened after this date exclusively used the profile hand depiction in the iconography of Zeus. The upward oriented profile hand became the norm throughout the east in 326/5 BC. The fact that a single reverse die preceded this change at Damaskos indicates that the mint opened at the time that this change was officially formalized through all the mints of the east, placing the start of the mint sometime in 326/5; a down dating of five years relative to that posited by Newell and Price.

13. This coin is a drachm of Sardes (Price 2558) from the writer's collection.

14. The inferred movement of engravers between mints has precedent. It may have been more widespread than is currently appreciated. E. T. Newell, *The Dated Alexander Coinage of Sidon and Ake* (Oxford: Oxford University, 1916), 53 and 1918: 8) noted the movement of an engraver from Sidon to Tyre (Ake of Newell) and subsequently to Tarsos. Taylor 2015: 56–67 inferred the movement of at least one engraver from Arados to Babylon in 321/20 associated with the start of the satrapal coinage of Seleukos. R. P. Miller and O. D. Hoover, "The Sardes mint under Seleucus I Nicator," *AJN* 22 (2010): 30–31 reported the probable transfer in 282 of an engraver with a military mint under Seleukos I from Seleukeia in Pieria to Sardis.

Most of the Damaskos emission portrays a *diphros* bearing two distinct struts, modelled on the field chair of the Persian Kings as described and illustrated by Zervos.¹⁵ At Damaskos a brief flirtation with the more usual single strut depiction (Type 2 rev. noted in the catalogue) by a new engraver to the mint (die engraver 5) was overturned and the double strut of the field chair reinstated for the remainder of the emission. After the experimentation associated with engraver 5, the portrayal of Zeus seated with parallel legs remained a constant at Damaskos. It did not evolve towards that of Zeus seated on a high backed throne with his right leg drawn back behind the left, an iconographic depiction that became widespread after 323. This suggests that the coinage of Damaskos ceased before the spread of these developments; a *possible terminus ante quem* of 324/3 for the Damaskos emission.

Table 4. Eastern mints: tetradrachm dies before the change in treatment of Zeus's right hand.

Mint	Start date	Obv. dies.	Rev. dies.	Change in hand	Data source
Myriandros	c. 330/29	10	25	Price 3223	Newell (1919)
Arados	c. 328/7	9	11	Price 3305	Duyrat (2005)
Arados II*	c. 328/7	11	29	Price 3424	This study
Karne	c. 327/6	2	2	Price 3429	This study
Byblos	c. 328/7	0	0	-	This study
Berytos	c. 321/0	0	0	-	This study
Sidon	333/2	9	18	Price 3475	Newell (1916)
Tyre	332/1	15	65	Price 3260	Newell (1916)
Damaskos	326/5	1	1	Price 3197	This study
Babylon	326/5	1	1	Price 3579	This study
Susa	c. 325/4	0	0	-	This study

* Arados II = Price 3424 attributed to Byblos by Price.

SIZE AND DURATION OF THE EMISSION

Fifty-four obverse dies and 300 reverse dies are represented in the catalogue. Six obverse dies, A30, A37, A45, A50, A53 and A54 are each represented by a single coin in the catalogue. The sample of obverse dies represented in the catalogue is reasonably complete, indicated by the high characteristic index (n/d) of 8.4 accompanied by a statistical coverage (C_{est}) of 0.99 (Table 5). Based

15. O. H. Zervos, "Near Eastern elements in the tetradrachms of Alexander the Great: The Eastern Mints," in *Greek Numismatics and Archaeology Essays in Honor of Margaret Thompson*, ed. O. Mørkholm and N. Waggoner (Wetteren: Cultura Press, 1979), 295–305.

on the geometrical method advocated by Esty,¹⁶ an estimated 61 original obverse dies were used in the mint, with a 95% confidence level of ± 3 dies (Table 5). Assuming an average obverse die life of 20,000 coins,¹⁷ struck at the Attic weight standard of 17.2 grams per tetradrachm (identical to the observed modal weight defined in Figure 2), this would represent a total coinage of around 807 Attic talents, or c. 2.1 metric tons of silver, struck into c. 1.22 million tetradrachms.

Table 5. Catalogue statistics.

	Obverse dies A	Reverse dies P
Sample size (<i>n</i>)	456	456
Observed Dies (<i>d</i>)	54	300
Singletons (<i>d</i> ₁)	6	190
Characteristic index (<i>n/d</i>)	8.44	1.52
Coverage (<i>Cest</i>)	0.99	0.58
Estimated Original Dies (<i>Dest</i>)	61.25	876.92
95% Confidence Interval	58.4–64.3	730.6–1,052.8

In view of Mørkholm's suggestion that the motivation to open a mint at Damaskos "was perhaps prompted by the accident that here Alexander acquired the rich booty left by Darius after Issus,"¹⁸ it is instructive to compare the estimated coined volume to that seized by Parmenion and his troops at Damaskos. Curtius (*Alexander* 3.13.16) records that at Damaskos, Parmenion's troops seized articles weighing 500 talents of wrought silver, plus coined money that amounted to 2,600 talents; a total of 3,100 talents of precious metal. This exceeds by almost a factor of four the volume of silver minted in the name of Alexander at Damaskos. The volume of wrought silver might be a more appropriate measure of the potential source material for the Damaskos tetradrachms, but this is around 57 percent of the estimated coined volume at Damaskos. The motivation to recoin earlier Achaemenid coins while still on the campaign that ultimately led to Gaugamela is doubtful. In any event, much of the captured Achaemenid coinage was probably in the form gold darics, the preferred coinage of the Great Kings. Yet, gold coinage does not figure in the output of the Damaskos mint.

More significantly, the ancient sources record that Alexander set aside the content of the royal Persian field depot at Damaskos for Parmenion and the

16. W. W. Esty, "The Geometric Model for Estimating the Number of Dies," in *Quantifying Monetary Supplies in Greco-Roman Times*, ed. F. de Callatay (Bari: Edipuglia, 2011), 43–58.

17. Callatay, "Quantifying," 9.

18. Mørkholm, *Early*, 46.

Thessalian cavalry to seize as reward for their valor: “Alexander sent them on this expedition purposely, wishing to have them enrich themselves” (Plutarch, *Alexander* 24.1–2). Under the circumstances, it is unlikely that the motivation to open the Alexander mint at Damaskos was the seizure of the Persian field treasury and depot. It is more likely that Parmenion and the Thessalian cavalry carried off the treasury at Damaskos with other plunder on the route to Gaugamela. It remains an open question as to why and by what means the Damaskos treasury was replenished, sufficient to strike c. 807 Attic talents of coinage in the period 326/5–325/4, and to what purpose this coinage was put.

Reverse to Obverse (P/A) Ratio

Table 6 summarizes the number of observed reverse dies associated with each obverse die. Although the average reverse to obverse die ratio (P/A) of the catalogue is 5.6, there is a wide dispersion in this ratio. Thirteen obverse dies were paired to 10 or more reverse dies; the maximum observed in the catalogue is die A14, which was paired to 16 reverse dies. Eight obverse dies each paired to a single reverse die are present in the catalogue. The Series 1 and Series 2 obverse dies that were used in a serial striking manner (A1–A2 and A5–A9) have an average P/A ratio of 3.0. This is little more than half of the average ratio of 5.9 derived from the balance of the obverse dies that were used as a shared inventory for the more extensive parallel striking.

Using observed die counts for the determination of the average reverse to obverse die ratio (P/A) potentially understates reality by a significant margin due to the small size of the sample of the original coinage. This is reflected in the low characteristic index (n/d) of 1.52 and the modest statistical coverage (C_{est}) of 0.58 for the sample of reverse dies (Table 5). Applying the geometric model to the observed reverse die count in order to estimate the original number of reverse dies commissioned at the mint paints a considerably different picture (Table 7, below). An estimated 877 original reverse dies were commissioned in the mint with an associated 95 percent confidence level of 731–1,053 reverse dies (the low and high estimates in Table 7, below). The statistically estimated P/A ratio is around 14.3, rather than the 5.6 determined from the observed obverse dies in the catalogue. Seen in this light, the P/A ratios of 10 or more that are observed for fourteen obverse dies (Table 6, below) are not exceptional. The statistically estimated P/A ratio of 14.3 implies an average estimated reverse die life of 1,398 coins (assuming an obverse die life of 20,000 coins). By way of contrast, the catalogue represents a sample rate of about 1 : 2,675 of the coins originally struck (456 coins from an estimated 1.22 million coins struck). As a result, many reverse dies will not be represented in the relatively modest sample of

the original coinage, to the extent that any new coin added to the catalogue has a 42 percent probability (*1-Cest*) of coming from a previously undocumented reverse die. This relatively modest sample rate of the output from all the reverse dies explains the perceived gaps in the parallel striking operation represented schematically in Table 1.

Table 6. Reverse dies per obverse die.

Obv. die	No. of Rev. dies	Obv. die	No. of Rev. dies
A1	2	A28	13
A2	4	A29	9
A3	9	A30	1
A4	3	A31	12
A5	2	A32	7
A6	2	A33	6
A7	1	A34	9
A8	3	A35	7
A9	8	A36	4
A10	10	A37	1
A11	10	A38	2
A12	10	A39	3
A13	13	A40	1
A14	16	A41	6
A15	7	A42	6
A16	2	A43	12
A17	10	A44	4
A18	12	A45	1
A19	2	A46	4
A20	8	A47	10
A21	2	A48	5
A22	6	A49	7
A23	13	A50	1
A24	9	A51	2
A25	13	A52	2
A26	6	A53	1
A27	6	A54	1

Shading denotes dies utilized in a serial manner.

Table 7: Statistically estimated original dies and P/A ratio.

Damaskos	P dies	A dies	P/A
Observed	300.0	54.0	5.6
Estimated	876.9	61.3	14.3
Low Estimate	730.6	58.4	12.5
High Estimate	1,052.8	64.3	16.4

In the Alexander mints that struck their coinage in a steady serial manner, the estimated original average die pairing (P/A) ratio is usually less than 7.7. Some process or factor appears to have operated in the newly opened mint at Damaskos that resulted in shorter reverse die lives than usually encountered in the contemporary mints of the littoral eastern Mediterranean. The best clue we have comes from the die study. With few exceptions, the catalogue coins show little evidence of significant reverse die wear, suggesting that most of the reverse dies were subject to fragmentation and fracture breakage before die wear advanced to a significant degree. Supporting this view is the fact that some of the reverse dies identified in the catalogue show early signs of fragmentation, but are little worn (Cat. Nos. 52–53, 56, 189, 215–217, 283, 318, 325 and 345). The observed pattern of fragmentation, with pieces breaking out of the unworn die, suggests that the die failure mechanism involved die alloy embrittlement.¹⁹ Remembering that the Damaskos mint had no precursor, it is possible that the bronze alloy from which the dies were made contained impurities leading to intergranular embrittlement in the alloy, or a less than optimum manufacturing process for the alloy may have caused greater embrittlement than usual. Under the stress of repeated heavy hammer blows, alloy embrittlement would result in the rapid growth and propagation of micro fractures, with little surface expression, sufficient to cause premature reverse die fragmentation, fracture and breakage, with little sign on the die's working surface, until the point of fragmen-

19. Probably bronze alloy dies were used, rather than steel dies, as evidenced by the complete absence of any indications of die rust on the struck coins. Most alloys, including bronze, can exhibit failure by cracking in circumstances where the apparent applied stress is well below that at which failure would normally be expected. Bronze (and steel) alloys are no exception to this, and probably exhibit a wider variety of failure mechanisms than any other category of material. There are several forms of embrittlement, including intergranular embrittlement and embrittlement caused by overheating during the hardening and tempering in the manufacture of dies. Without detailed knowledge of the nature of the dies involved, their metallic composition and details of manufacture, it is not possible to be more precise about the nature of the embrittlement and the resultant rate of progression to fracture failure and fragmentation under the stress of repeated heavy hammer blows and the resultant accumulation of strain in the die.

tation failure. As the anvil die was subject to less stress loading, it would be less prone to this failure mechanism, although some obverse dies in the catalogue also show evidence of fragmentation failure (A3 Cat. Nos. 40–41, A20 Cat. Nos. 129–136, A47 throughout catalogue, A53 Cat. No. 332, A48 Cat. No. 348, A32 Cat. No. 405 and A38 Cat. Nos. 415–416). These observations suggest that embrittlement was a factor on both obverse and reverse dies, but its consequences were more profound for the reverse dies, which received directly repeated, heavy hammer blows.

Another contributing factor to premature reverse die breakage may have been the high volume of production from multiple striking teams in a competitive environment. This could have resulted in the mishandling of reverse dies with greater stresses imposed on the punch die, contributing to earlier die failure than occurred in the more leisurely serial striking of an annual issue that was often the norm elsewhere. Possible support for this is found in the increase of the observed average reverse to obverse die ratio of 3.0 for the coinage struck serially, to 5.9 for the coinage struck on multiple anvils. This subject goes well beyond the scope of this paper to explore in depth. Suffice to note it here because of its implications for the mint's production process. A corollary of the statistically estimated reverse die life is that an average of four to five new reverse dies would need to have been commissioned daily (plus a new obverse die every three days) at the peak of the mint's productivity, with six anvils in operation (i.e. an output of c. 6,000 coins per day). This requirement for frequent reverse die replacement goes some way to explain the fact that up to nine die engravers were engaged during the emission.

Production Duration

Using the assumption of an average 20,000 coins per obverse die, and a daily striking rate for a single striking team of c. 1,000 coins per day²⁰ we can make some estimate of the minimum time in which the coinage could have been struck. The initial serial striking stage of each of Series 1 and Series 2 involved two and five obverse dies respectively. This generates a minimum duration for

20. Studies of Roman coinage and the results of modern experimental striking studies suggest that a rate of up to ten times this may have been achievable in the production of denarius coinage. Larger denomination Hellenistic coinage production rates are likely to have been appreciably lower. Rather than the physical striking of a coin, the bottleneck that constrained a daily coinage production rate was the manufacture of blanks involving the fusion of a precisely measured weight of precious metal into a coin blank, preparatory to striking. This most certainly took longer than the seconds taken to complete a coin strike, so that in all likelihood the production rate per anvil was constrained by the rate of manufacture of the blanks for striking.

Figure 1. Metrology.

this commissioning stage of the mint's operation of c. 100 days. The subsequent extensive parallel striking stage involving the last two dies of Series 1, plus 45 dies of Series 2, could have been achieved in as little as 156 days for a continuous six-anvil production operation.

This suggests the possibility that the entire Damaskos output could have occurred within as little as one year of continuous multi-anvil operation of the type implied in the catalogue and Table 1. Two years' duration would imply a rather relaxed striking operation, arguably inconsistent with the massively interwoven, obverse die-linked nature of the coinage in the catalogue. This places a lower to upper limit of 1–2 years on the duration of production of the Damaskos 'Alexanders' with the considered opinion of the author being a likely duration closer to one year in the period 326/5–325/4.

METROLOGY

The distribution of tetradrachm weights in the catalogue (Fig. 1), shows that the weight was tightly controlled, with a pronounced mode in the range 17.20–17.24 grams. The distribution of weights conforms to the Attic weight standard with a notably small dispersion. This indicates that a high level of quality control was maintained in the manufacture of silver coin blanks, throughout the mintage. A similarly high level of quality control is evident in the striking of the

coins, to the extent that with relatively few exceptions the die axes are consistently oriented between 11h and 1h, while the strikes generally are well centred.

It appears that the Damaskos mint struck coins to a consistently high standard from the outset, with no tangible evidence of an initial learning curve, despite no prior history of mintage in the city. This is indirect evidence for the probable importation of experienced mint workers from other regional mints in preference to the more gradual development of local expertise in mint operations.

HOARD RECORD

Summarized in Table 8 is the hoard data relevant to the Damaskos coinage. All the Damaskos types are represented in the Demanhur Hoard (*IGCH* 1664) that closed in 318. The earliest hoard bearing a Damaskos tetradrachm dates to 323 (*IGCH* 1436). Issues down to sequence type 2.7.1 are represented in the earliest hoards, dated to 323–320, consistent with the interpretation that the entire coinage was struck before the death of Alexander the Great. Apparently, a few of the Damaskos coins continued to circulate down to the second century BC as indicated by the Latakia Hoard (*IGCH* 1544).

It is notable that there is only one documented find of Damaskos types east of the city, the Failaka Hoard (CH 10.264) that closed in 285. Most of the coinage appears to have circulated rapidly to regions to the west of the city. The westernmost find is the Andritsaena Hoard in Elis, Greece (*IGCH* 0083) that closed in 315–310. The southwestern most find is that of the Demanhur Hoard (*IGCH* 1664) that closed in 318. It contained 369 Damaskos coins, exceeding the cumulative total of all other recorded finds by a factor of five. To the north the farthest outlier find is the Anadol Hoard (*IGCH* 0866) in the Ukraine that closed 228–220.

There are no recorded finds in the immediate vicinity of Damaskos. Rather, it appears that a rapid and wide western dispersion of the coinage occurred. The closest recorded find to the city is that of a solitary coin of Damaskos amongst 118 coins in the Khirbet el-Kerak Hoard (*IGCH* 1510) in Galilee, dated to 319. This is c. 125 km to the southwest of Damaskos.

Table 8. Hoards.

Hoard	Closure (BC)	Location	Damaskos content
<i>IGCH</i> 1436	323	Asia Minor	1
<i>CH</i> 8.185	323	Syria or Lebanon	2
<i>CH</i> 8.189	323–320	Unknown	3
<i>CH</i> 8.193	320	Thessaly	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1438	320	Asia Minor	4
<i>IGCH</i> 1421	320	Cilicia	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1510	319	Khirbet el-Kerak, Galilee	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1664	318	Demanhur, Egypt	369
<i>CH</i> 10.251	318/7	Akçakale, Turkey	3
<i>IGCH</i> 1443	317/6	Asia Minor	1
<i>IGCH</i> 0082	315	Kardista, Thessaly	1
<i>IGCH</i> 0084	315–310	Tripolis, Arcadia	1
<i>IGCH</i> 0083	315–310	Andritsaena, Elis	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1667	311–310	Abu Hommos, Egypt	7
<i>IGCH</i> 1468	310	Kannaviou, Cyprus	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1670	310–305	Kuft, Egypt	3
<i>IGCH</i> 1516	305	Aleppo, Syria	21
<i>IGCH</i> 0093	310–300	Lamia, Thessaly	1
Zlotnik, <i>INR</i> 5	300–295	Syria	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1399	290–285	Ankara, Galatia	2
<i>IGCH</i> 0443	290–280	Macedonia	1
<i>CH</i> 10.264	285	Failaka, Kuwait	4
<i>IGCH</i> 1678	283	Phacous, Egypt	17
<i>CH</i> 10.265	281	Asia Minor	4
<i>IGCH</i> 0448	280	Prilepec, Yugoslavia	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1293	280	Manissa, Lydia	1
<i>IGCH</i> 1403	250	Gordion, Phrygia	2
<i>IGCH</i> 0866	228–220	Anadol, Ukraine	2
<i>IGCH</i> 0181	222	Sparta, Laconia	1
<i>IGCH</i> 0458	220	Zemun, Serbia	1
<i>IGCH</i> 0867	220	Büyükçekmece, Thrace	1 (?)
<i>IGCH</i> 1544	169	Latakia, Syria	1

CONCLUSION

The catalogue and die study point to the likelihood that the mint was established no earlier than 326/5. The redeployment of skilled mint workers from other regional mints may have facilitated its establishment. As the resources of the mint expanded, a brief initial stage of serial utilisation of dies in two workshops was rapidly supplanted by an expanded number of striking teams and anvils, shortly after which Series 1 was completely eclipsed by Series 2 struck on six anvils. The life of the mint was limited to a brief period in the last years of Alexander III's lifetime, during which time it produced an estimated 1.22 million tetradrachms. Based on conservative estimates of die life and the closely die linked interwoven nature of coinage, it is inferred that that the mint may have operated for little more than a year after its establishment. Its coinage then dispersed rapidly to the west, arguably consistent with the dispersal pattern of military payments made to demobilized Greek veterans at the end of their service to Alexander the Great.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study most certainly rests upon the shoulders of a giant, Edward T. Newell. Without his collection, bequeathed to the American Numismatic Society, the record of the coinage of Damaskos would have been scattered to the wind. Almost a century after his initial studies, Newell's hand guided the die study, in so far as his trays of sorted Damaskos Alexanders provided a foundation for the framework presented here. Without the generosity, innovation and effort of the American Numismatic Society in making not only its collection, but those of the British Museum, the Bibliothèque Nationale de France and the Münzkabinett Berlin, internationally accessible via the PELLA database, it would have been much more difficult to undertake this work from a remote location. The generous assistance Dr. Ute Wartenberg Kagan and Brad Nelson in reviewing and commenting on the paper is gratefully acknowledged. My wife Colleen showed great forbearance as I endlessly compared, sorted and catalogued images of the coins. Finally, I dedicate this work to the memory of Eike Taylor whose spirit of joyous inquiry and energy sustained the author in the year following his passing. He was my epiphany on the road to Damaskos.

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Plate 6

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The Damaskos Mint of Alexander the Great

Plate 8

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The Damaskos Mint of Alexander the Great

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The Damaskos Mint of Alexander the Great

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The Damaskos Mint of Alexander the Great

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The Damaskos Mint of Alexander the Great

Plate 14

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